

Implications of Eurocode 7 for Geotechnical Design in Ireland

Trevor L.L. ORR, BA, BAI, MSc, PhD, Eurling
Chartered Engineer and Senior Lecturer, Trinity College Dublin

Summary of paper presented to a meeting of the Geotechnical Society of Ireland Society at the Institution of Engineers of Ireland on 4th November 2002

SYNOPSIS

Eurocode 7, the new harmonised European code for geotechnical design, is due to be introduced in Ireland in 2004. This code is very different from the existing codes for geotechnical design as it is a comprehensive limit state design code based on the use of partial factors with three design approaches. In this paper, the implications of introducing Eurocode 7, with its requirements for all the different aspects of geotechnical design, including ground investigations, the selection of parameter values, design calculations and construction monitoring, are examined. Three examples, involving spread foundations, pile foundation and a retaining wall, are presented to demonstrate the use of Eurocode 7 and to compare the results obtained using the different design approaches with those obtained using the traditional design method and an overall factor of safety. Before Eurocode 7 can be introduced in Ireland, an Irish National Annex will need to be prepared providing the information, such as which design approach or approaches and which partial factors are required to use Eurocode 7 in Ireland. It is concluded that the introduction of Eurocode 7 will clarify the geotechnical design process, resulting in more rational designs, and will enhance the role and image of geotechnical design by harmonising it with structural design and with geotechnical design in other European countries.

1 Objective

The objective of this paper is to assess the implications of introducing Eurocode 7: Part 1 for geotechnical design in Ireland. The paper examines the main features of Eurocode 7, including the limit state design philosophy and the three Design Approaches with different sets of partial factors. In order to illustrate the effects of using the different Design Approaches, three examples, consisting of a spread foundation, a pile foundation and a retaining wall, are presented. This paper also examines the information that will need to be provided in the Irish National Annex, such as which Design Approach or Approaches are to be used and the values of the partial factors, in order to introduce Eurocode 7 in Ireland.

2 Eurocode System

In 1975, the European Commission started an action programme to eliminate the technical obstacles to trade in construction in Europe due to different national codes, standards and technical specifications. Within this programme, the Eurocodes were conceived as a set of codes providing harmonised technical rules for the structural and geotechnical design of buildings and civil engineering works in the different construction materials; i.e. concrete, steel, masonry, timber and aluminium and geotechnical materials (soil and rock). Eurocode 7, Part 1 provides the general rules for geotechnical design.

The head Eurocode in 1994, ENV 1991-1: Eurocode 1, which set out the basic philosophy for all the Eurocodes, stated that the Eurocodes would initially serve as alternatives to the different rules in the member states and ultimately would replace them. The new head Eurocode, EN 1990: 2001, which is now a full European standard, states that

the intended status of the Eurocodes is they should serve as reference documents for the following purposes:

- to prove compliance of buildings and civil engineering works with the essential requirements of the European Directive on Construction Products
- as a basis for specifying contracts for construction works and related engineering services
- as a framework for drawing up harmonised technical specifications for construction products (ENs - European Standards, and ETAs - European Technical Agreements)

In view of the aims and status for the Eurocodes stated in ENV 1991 and EN 1990, the objectives of Eurocode 7 are therefore:

- The harmonisation of geotechnical design in the countries of Europe by providing a single design code to replace the different national geotechnical design codes used at present
- The harmonisation of geotechnical design with structural design through the Eurocodes providing harmonised technical rules for the design of buildings and civil engineering works.
- The role of Eurocode 7 in harmonising geotechnical design has been examined by Orr(2002).

3 Eurocode 7: Part 1

Work on Eurocode 7: Part 1 started in 1981 with a committee consisting of representatives from the 9 EEC countries (later 11) having N. Krebs Ovesen as the convener. The progress on the development of Eurocode 7 has been as follows:

1994 - Prestandard (ENV) version published as Eurocode 7: Part 1 – Geotechnical Design: General Rules. After a four-year period for trial use, the full European Standard

(EN) version has been prepared, taking into account national comments received, and is now about to be published.

2003 - Formal vote by CEN for approval of Eurocode 7: Part 1 as an EN

2004 - Publication of national standard versions of Eurocode 7 with national annexes, including the Irish Standard (IS) version with the Irish National Annex. This will be followed by a limited period of coexistence before the IS version of Eurocode 7 replaces the existing geotechnical standards, e.g. BS 8002 and BS 8004.

4 Eurocode 7: Part 2

As the determination of soil properties is part of the geotechnical design process, Eurocode 7: Part 2 - Ground Investigations and Testing is being prepared. Part 2 is not a testing standard, but will provide code requirements for the following aspects of geotechnical design:

- The determination of parameter values for use in geotechnical designs
- The planning of geotechnical investigations
- The most commonly used field and laboratory tests,
- The interpretation of test results and geotechnical data and the determination of the values of geotechnical parameters.

5 Structure of Eurocode 7: Part 1

The EN version of Eurocode 7: Part 1 consists of the following 12 sections:

- Section 1: General
- Section 2: Basis of geotechnical design
- Section 3: Geotechnical data
- Section 4: Supervision of construction, monitoring and maintenance
- Section 5: Fill, dewatering and ground improvement

- Section 6: Shallow foundations
- Section 7: Pile foundations
- Section 8: Anchorages
- Section 9: Earth retaining structures
- Section 10: Hydraulic failure
- Section 11: Overall stability
- Section 12: Embankments

There are also the following 7 Annexes:

- Annex A: Safety factors for ultimate limit states
- Annex B: Background information on partial factors for Design Approaches 1, 2 and 3
- Annex C: Sample procedures to determine limit values of earth pressures on vertical walls
- Annex D: A sample analytical method for bearing resistance estimation
- Annex E: A sample semi-empirical method for bearing resistance estimation
- Annex F: Sample methods for settlement evaluation
- Annex G: A sample method for deriving presumed bearing resistance for spread foundations on rock
- Annex H: Limiting foundation movements and structural deformation
- Annex J: Checklist for construction supervision and performance monitoring.

Annex A, with the safety factors for ultimate limit states, is a normative annex, and hence the values of the partial factors are code requirements, while all the other annexes are informative and hence not code requirements but provide for guidance and information.

Eurocode 7: Part 1 provides the principles for geotechnical design and general guidance on the application of these principles. There are very few equations or calculation methods in the main part of Eurocode 7. The informative annexes, however, provide some equations and some more specific guidance, e.g.

- Bearing resistance equations
- Earth pressure equations
- A checklist for supervision and monitoring.

The text of Eurocode 7 is divided into:

- Principles, which are general statements and definitions for which there is no alternative, and requirements and analytical models for which no alternative is permitted unless specifically stated; and
- Application rules, which are examples of generally recognised rules, which follow the principles and satisfy their requirements.

6 Terminology

The introduction of Eurocode 7 for geotechnical design in Ireland will involve the use of some Eurocode terminology that is not commonly used in geotechnical design in Ireland. Such terminology includes:

- *Action*: Defined as a force or imposed displacement that is a known quantity the designer shall choose or determine before carrying out a calculation.
- *Geotechnical Action*: Defined as an action transmitted to the structure by the ground, fill or groundwater.
- *Comparable experience*: Defined as documented or clearly established information related to the ground being considered in design, involving the same types of soil or rock and for which similar geotechnical behaviour is expected, and involving similar structures. *Single source*: Since the weight of the soil or groundwater pressure may give rise to both favourable and unfavourable actions, e.g. in slope stability and retaining wall situations, if the resultant action due to the weight of the soil or groundwater pressure is treated as coming from a single source, then the same partial factor is applied to both the favourable and unfavourable actions.

7 Design Process

With regard to the geotechnical design process and its various stages, Eurocode 7: Part 1 provides the requirements for, and guidance on, the extent and quality of the following aspects:

- Geotechnical investigations
 - Ground investigation reports
 - Geotechnical design reports
 - Design calculations
 - Construction control checks, and
 - Monitoring and maintenance of the completed structure
- Thus Eurocode 7 is a comprehensive code that is concerned with the entire geotechnical design process. This process is explained by Orr & Farrell (1999). The importance of adequate continuity and communication between persons involved in the different stages of the design process is emphasized.

8 Design Complexity and Geotechnical Categories

The first stage in a geotechnical design is to assess the complexity of a particular design situation. The complexity can vary greatly from very simple to very complex design situations. According to Eurocode 7, the factors to be taken into account when assessing the complexity of a geotechnical design are:

- Ground conditions
- Groundwater conditions
- Regional seismicity
- Influence of the environment
- Nature and size of the structure
- Conditions with regard to the surroundings.

The concept of Geotechnical Categories is offered in Eurocode 7 as a method for taking into account the different levels of complexity of a geotechnical design. Three geotechnical categories are presented, Geotechnical Categories 1, 2 and 3, which are defined as follows:

- Geotechnical Category 1 is small relatively simple structures on ground conditions

which are known from experience to be straightforward and do not involve soft, loose or compressible soil, loose fill or sloping ground

- Geotechnical Category 2 is conventional types of structures and foundations with no exceptional risk or difficult soil or loading conditions
- Geotechnical Category 3 is very large structures on unusual or exceptionally difficult ground conditions.

The use of the Geotechnical Categories is not a code requirement, but is presented in an application rule and so is optional. One of the implications of the introduction of Eurocode 7 in Ireland could be the adoption, into geotechnical design practice, of system of Geotechnical Categories. This system provides a framework with the following guidelines on how to satisfy the minimum requirements for geotechnical designs to Eurocode 7 in the case of design situations with different levels of complexity:

- In the case of light and simple structures and small earthworks, i.e. Geotechnical Category 1, the minimum requirements will be satisfied by comparable experience, qualitative geotechnical investigations, simplified design procedures and prescriptive measures. Eurocode 7 does not, and cannot, provide detailed provisions or guidance for Geotechnical Category 1. Hence the manner in which the minimum requirements for these structures will be satisfied in each country will need to be determined nationally. Before Eurocode 7 can be implemented in Ireland, it will be necessary to specify:
 - What simplified design procedures will be permitted, and
 - What prescriptive measures will be acceptable.
- In the case of most structures without abnormal loads or difficult ground conditions, i.e.

Geotechnical Category 2, the minimum requirements involve routine procedures for field and laboratory investigations and routine calculations based on the design procedures in Eurocode 7. Indeed Eurocode 7 is chiefly concerned with the provisions for Geotechnical Category 2. In the case of large structures and complex ground conditions, i.e. Geotechnical Category 3, the minimum requirements in Eurocode 7 for Geotechnical Category 2 also apply. Apart from the Geotechnical Category 2 provisions, Eurocode 7 does not provide any additional special requirements for Geotechnical Category 3. Normally, however, Geotechnical Category 3 will require the involvement of a specialist, additional testing and more sophisticated analyses.

9 Limit State Design

Eurocode 7 is based on the limit state design philosophy, with partial factors, set out in EN 1990: Basis of Design. According to this philosophy, it is necessary to check that the occurrence of two limit states, ultimate and serviceability limit states, is sufficiently unlikely.

Ultimate limit states are situations which involve safety, such as the collapse of a structure or any other type of failure. These include excessive deformation in the ground prior to failure causing failure in the supported structure, or situations where there is a risk of damage to people or severe economic loss. Ultimate limit states have a low probability of occurrence for properly designed structures.

Serviceability limit states are situations where specified requirements of the structure are no longer met. These requirements include deformations, settlements, vibrations, and local damage of the structure in normal use under working loads. Serviceability limit states

have a higher probability of occurrence than ultimate limit states in a properly designed structure.

When designing to Eurocode 7, it is necessary to consider all possible failure modes and to verify that no relevant limit state is exceeded. Geotechnical designs to Eurocode 7 may be checked by one or a combination of the following four designs methods:

- Use of calculations. This is the most common method.
- Adoption of prescriptive measures. Prescriptive measures include, for example, minimum foundation depths to avoid frost damage
- Use of experimental models and load tests. The use of load tests recommended with calculations for pile design.
- Use of an observational method.

The inclusion of the observational method as a design method is important novel feature of Eurocode 7 and, if availed of, could have important implications for geotechnical design in Ireland, offering a more important role for geotechnics in order to achieve more economic designs and shorter construction times in difficult ground conditions.

The importance of experience, particularly of local ground conditions and similar designs, is stressed in the case of all the design methods. This type of experience is termed 'comparable experience'.

Limit state design calculations should be carried out using models that describe the behaviour of the ground for the states limit state under consideration. Hence separate and different calculations should be carried out when checking ultimate and serviceability limit state. Ultimate limit state calculations normally involve analysing a mechanism and using ground strength properties, while serviceability limit state

Figure 1: General procedure for obtaining design geotechnical parameters from measured values

calculations normally involve a deformation analysis.

10 Geotechnical Parameters

The selection of the appropriate ground parameter values for use in design calculations from values determined in field or laboratory tests is part of the design process and therefore the requirements for the selection of geotechnical parameter values are given in Parts 1 and 2 of Eurocode 7. The values used in design calculations are termed design values and these are obtained from tests results via derived values and characteristic values as shown in Figure 1. Test results are results obtained from

field or laboratory tests while derived values are the values of geotechnical parameters obtained by theory, correlation or empiricism from test results.

The characteristic value of a strength parameter is defined in EN 1990 as the 5% fractile value of the assumed statistical distribution of the property in a hypothetical unlimited test series. This definition is appropriate for manufactured materials, such as concrete or steel. However, in geotechnical design, a statistical approach is not normally appropriate because of the limited number of available test results and the variability of soil. Hence the definition of the characteristic

value of a geotechnical parameter given in Eurocode 7 which is a cautious estimate of the value affecting the occurrence of the limit state. If statistics are used, the characteristic value is derived such that the calculated probability of a worse value governing the occurrence of a limit state is not greater than 5%.

When selecting characteristic values it is necessary, as noted in Figure 1, to take account of the design situation, including:

- The particular limit state being considered
- The volume of ground involved
- The ability of the ground to distribute the load within the structure.

When a limit state involves a local failure with a small volume of soil, then a more cautious characteristic value should be chosen than when the limit state involves a large slip surface and a large volume of ground. This is illustrated by the example in Figure 2 of the selection of the larger characteristic c_u value for a general slip failure than the smaller, more cautious, c_u value selected for a local failure.

11 Common Partial Factors

Since the Eurocodes are intended to serve as a harmonised set of codes for structural and geotechnical designs, a key feature of the Eurocodes is the common set of partial factors for actions for all designs provided in the head code, EN 1990: Eurocode Basis of design. The partial material factors for designs involving different materials are provided in the material codes, e.g. Eurocode 7 provides the partial factors for geotechnical designs involving soil.

The common set of partial factors for actions in the Eurocodes has given rise to considerable debate in development of Eurocode 7. This has arisen because, in structural designs, partial factors greater than unity (e.g. 1.35) are normally used for unfavourable permanent actions. However, in geotechnical designs, partial factors equal to unity are normally used for permanent actions, e.g. loads due to soil weight, because there is normally much more uncertainty about the strength of the ground than about its weight. Also, in many design situations, loads due to the weight of soil may be both favourable and unfavourable, e.g. in slope stability and retaining wall analyses, and hence it is not appropriate, or indeed often even possible, to apply different partial factors to different parts of the soil weight.

Figure 2: Characteristic c_u values for different design situations

12 Design Calculations

In ultimate limit state design calculations, Eurocode 7 requires that the following equilibrium equation is satisfied:

$$E_d \leq R_d \quad (1)$$

where E_d is the design action and R_d is the design resistance. Thus Eurocode 7 requires the designer to check equilibrium of design (factored) forces and design resistances for each design situation. In this system it is necessary for the designer to distinguish clearly between actions and resistance and to work with forces rather than stresses. This is different to many conventional geotechnical design calculations where stresses in the ground due to working (unfactored) loads are compared to allowable stresses. Thus the introduction of Eurocode 7 will result in a change from conventional practice in these design situations and, in the author's view, will help clarify the design process.

13 Ultimate Limit States

Eurocode 7 lists the following five ultimate limit states that need to be checked in geotechnical designs

- EQU: loss of equilibrium of the structure or ground considered as a rigid body; the strength of the ground is insignificant in providing resistance in this ultimate limit state
- STR: internal failure or excessive deformation of the structure or structural elements, including footings, retaining walls, etc, in which the strength of structural materials is significant in providing resistance
- GEO: failure or excessive deformation of the ground, in which the strength of soil or rock is significant in providing resistance
- UPL: loss of equilibrium of the structure or ground due to uplift by water pressure
- HYD: hydraulic heave in the ground caused by hydraulic gradients.

The limit states EQU, STR and GEO apply to both structural and geotechnical designs, and hence

Design Approach	1.1	1.2	1.3	2	3s	3g
<i>Partial Load factors (γ_F)</i>						
Permanent unfavourable load	1.35	1.00	1.00	1.35	1.35	1.00
Permanent favourable action	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Variable unfavourable action	1.50	1.30	1.00	1.50	1.50	1.30
<i>Partial material factors (γ_m)</i>						
Tan ϕ'	1.00	1.25	1.00	1.00		1.25
Effective cohesion, c'	1.00	1.25	1.00	1.00		1.25
Undrained shear strength	1.00	1.40	1.00	1.00		1.40
<i>Partial resistance factors (γ_R)</i>						
Bearing resistance	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.40		1.00
Sliding resistance	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.10		1.00
Driven pile base resistance	1.00	-*	1.30	1.10		1.00
Driven pile shaft resistance	1.00	-*	1.30	1.10		1.00

*Partial factors not relevant and hence not provided for DA1.2

Table 1: Partial Factors for STR and GEO Ultimate Limit States for persistent and transient design situations

Provide harmony between geotechnical and structural design. Limit states UPL and HYD are only relevant to situations involving groundwater and hence only apply to geotechnical designs. The partial factors for verifying all these limit states are given in separate tables in Annex 1 of Eurocode 7: Part 1 and are summarised in the following sections.

13.1 EQU: Ultimate Limit States

In EQU ultimate limit states it is necessary to check that:

$$E_{dst,d} \leq E_{stb,d} \quad (2)$$

where $E_{dst,d}$ is the destabilising action and $E_{stb,d}$ is the stabilizing action. The values of the partial factors to obtain these design actions are:

Permanent actions, γ_G :

Unfavourable actions = 1.10

Favourable actions = 0.90

Variable actions, γ_Q :

Unfavourable actions = 1.50

Favourable actions = 0.0

EQU limit states are rarely relevant in geotechnical engineering. Examples include overturning of retaining walls on rock and overturning of rocks.

13.2 STR and GEO Ultimate Limit States

The partial factors for actions, ground properties and resistances for STR and GEO ultimate limit states are the same. In GEO ultimate limit states it is necessary to check that:

$$E_d \leq R_d \quad (3)$$

where E_d is the design action and R_d is the design resistance. The design resistance may be determined using three approaches: Design Approach 1(DA1), Design Approach 2(DA2) and Design Approach 3(DA3). The sets of γ factors for actions, material properties and resistances for each Design Approach are shown in Table 1 and discussed in the following paragraphs.

Design Approach 1

In Design Approach 1 the γ factors are generally applied to the actions and material properties, except in the case of piles and anchors where γ is applied to the resistances. Two calculations are generally required with the 2 combinations of γ factors, Combinations 1.1 and 1.2 in Table 1, which are similar to the former Cases B and C of ENV 1997-1. In the first calculation, the Combination 1

set of γ factors is applied mainly to actions, while in the second calculation, the Combination 2 set of γ factors is applied mainly to the material properties.

Design Approach 2

In Design Approach 1 the γ factors are generally applied to the actions or action effects and to the resistances, except for slope stability problems, where γ is applied to the material properties. Only one calculation is required using this approach.

Design Approach 3

Design Approach 3 is similar to Design Approach 1 but γ is always applied to the actions and material properties, except for the tensile resistance of pile foundations, and different γ factors are applied to structural and geotechnical loads. Like Design Approach 2, only one calculation is required.

Design Approaches 2 & 3, with one set of γ factors, were introduced to allow just one calculation, rather than the two required for Design Approach 1. Design Approach 2 was introduced to allow greater use of partial factors on resistances as an alternative to partial factors on material parameters and also

because, with partial factors mostly on resistances, it is closer to traditional global factor design. In order to introduce Eurocode 7, each country will have to decide and state in its National Annex which Design Approach or Approaches are to be used in its country.

13.3 UPL Ultimate Limit States

UPL ultimate limit states are concerned with failure due to uplift by hydrostatic pressure without seepage. In this case it is necessary to check that:

$$V_{dsb,d} \leq G_{stb,d} \quad (4)$$

where $V_{dsb,d}$ is the design value of the combination of the destabilizing permanent and variable actions and $G_{stb,d}$ is the design value of the combination of stabilising permanent actions. The values of the partial factors to obtain these design actions are:

Permanent actions, γ_G :	
Unfavourable actions	= 1.10
Favourable actions	= 0.90
Variable actions, γ_Q :	
Unfavourable actions	= 1.50
Favourable actions	= 0.0
Material Properties & Resistances, γ_m & γ_R :	
$\tan\phi'$	= 1.25
c'	= 1.25
Tensile pile resistance	= 1.40

13.4 HYD Ultimate Limit States

HYD ultimate limit states are concerned with failure due to heave of the ground caused by seepage due to hydraulic gradients. In this case stability against failure can be checked by comparing either the design pore pressure, u_d and design total stress, σ_d at the base of a soil column, or else the design seepage force, S_d on the column and the design submerged weight, G'_d of the column; i.e.

$$u_{dsb,d} \leq \sigma_d \quad (5a)$$

$$V_d \leq G'_d \quad (5b)$$

The values of the partial factors to obtain these design actions are:

Permanent actions, γ_G :	
Unfavourable actions	= 1.35
Favourable actions	= 0.90
Variable actions, γ_Q :	
Unfavourable actions	= 1.50

No partial factors are given for piping failure. Instead it is recommended that piping failure should be avoided by adopting prescriptive measures such as:

- The use of filters
- Preventing seepage
- Increasing the seepage path length.

14 National Annex

In order for Eurocode 7 to be implemented in Ireland as an Irish Standard, the National Standards Institution of Ireland, NSAI, which is the national member of CEN, needs to prepare a National Annex that specifies the national safety elements for geotechnical design in Ireland. An Irish Eurocode 7 Mirror Group, chaired by Dr. Eric Farrell, has been established by NSAI to prepare this National Annex. This Mirror Group will establish the specific requirements and safety elements necessary to implement Eurocode 7 in Ireland. Examples of these requirements and elements include:

- The minimum requirements for design of light and simple structures and small earthworks
- Whether and, if so, how the system of geotechnical categories will be introduced.
- What prescriptive measures will be recommended
- Which Design Approach(es) will be recommended for different design situations, and
- What partial factors will be recommended.

15 Design Examples

The following three design examples were chosen to illustrate some of the implications of introducing Eurocode 7 in Ireland:

- A spread foundation
- A pile foundation, and
- A retaining wall.

15.1 Spread Foundation

The spread foundation example consists of a square foundation founded at a depth of 1m and supporting a central vertical permanent load of 200kN and a central vertical variable load of 80kN. The soil is uniform dry sand with $c' = 0$ and a weight density of 20kN/m^3 .

The purpose of this example is to compare the design widths obtained using the traditional method and an overall factor of safety (FOS) of 3, with the foundation widths obtained using the three Eurocode 7 Design Approaches as ϕ' varies from 20° to 40° . The results plotted in Figure 3 show that:

- All the Design Approaches give smaller foundation widths than the traditional design method.
- Design Approach 3 gives larger widths than Design Approaches 1.2 or 2.
- For $\phi' > 25^\circ$, Design Approach 1.2 gives larger widths than Design Approach 2. This is beneficial because for $\phi' > 25^\circ$ the design foundation size is more sensitive to errors in ϕ' .
- Design Approach 1.2 gives smaller widths than Design Approach 2 for $\phi' < 25^\circ$.
- The calculated overall factor of safety (FOS) for Design Approach 1.2 ranges from 1.6 to 2.5.
- For low ϕ' values, when the FOS is smallest and the foundation size largest, the foundation size is more likely to be controlled by settlements, and hence SLS requirements, than by ULS requirements.

The implications of adopting Eurocode 7 for the design of foundations in Ireland are that:

- Calculations are in terms of loads rather than bearing pressures as in designs using the traditional method.
- The design calculations are simpler than those used in the traditional method as there is no need to calculate net bearing pressures.
- The distinction between loads and resistances is clarified.
- In Design Approach 1, the partial actors are placed on the material parameters and so are closer to the source of the uncertainty. This is important as bearing resistance and also earth pressure are non-linear functions of ϕ' .

Figure 3: Variation in foundation width with ϕ' for different design approaches

15.2 Pile Foundations

In the design of pile foundations to Eurocode 7, the emphasis is on the use of pile load tests. For Design Approaches 1 and 2, partial factors are applied to pile resistances rather than to soil strength parameters. The characteristic pile resistance is determined from the measured pile resistances using correlation factors ξ that are a function of the number of pile load tests. The ξ factors are presented in Table 2. These values demonstrate the benefit of carrying out more pile load tests since, with more tests and hence more confidence in the test results, higher characteristic values are obtained.

15.3 Retaining Wall

The retaining wall example consists of a 4m high retaining, propped at the top and supporting ground with a surcharge of 10kPa. The soil is uniform dry sand with $c' = 0$ and a weight density of 20kN/m^3 . The purpose of this example is to compare the design embedment depths of the wall obtained using the traditional method, with an FOS of 2, and the embedment depths obtained using the three

Eurocode 7 Design Approaches, as ϕ' varies from 20° to 40° . The results plotted in Figure 4 show that:

- Design Approach 3 gives similar depths to Design Approach 1.2
- Design Approach 1.2 gives smaller depths than DA2 for $\phi' < 33^\circ$
- Design Approach 1.2 gives larger depths than Design Approach 2 for $\phi' > 33^\circ$
- For large ϕ' values, the design more sensitive to errors in ϕ' , hence Design Approach 1.2 is safer.
- The traditional method, with a factor of safety of 2 on the passive earth pressure, gives the smallest depths of all the methods, except for ϕ' less than 23° , due mainly to there being no allowance for overdig.

ξ for n =	1	2	3	4	≥ 5
ξ_1	1.40	1.30	1.25	1.05	1.00
ξ_2	1.40	1.20	1.05	1.00	1.00

Table 2: Correlation factors, ξ to derive characteristic values from static pile load tests (n = number of pile load tests)

16 Advantages of Eurocode 7

Some of the advantages of introducing Eurocode 7 are:

- It provides a good set of principles and a rational and consistent framework for geotechnical design.
- It requires designers to focus on all the limit states which may affect a particular structure.
- It provides a clear distinction between ultimate and serviceability limit states. This does not occur with global factors of safety where often the magnitude of the factor of safety is chosen to limit deformations as well as to prevent collapse.
- It draws attention to the various factors that need to be considered in any particular design situation.
- It clarifies aspects that can cause confusion, such as the distinction between loads (actions) and resistances, and the selection of the appropriate parameter values to be used in design calculations.

17 Conclusions

The introduction of the Eurocodes in Ireland, with Eurocode 7 for geotechnical design, will provide a comprehensive framework for geotechnical design with a single code to cover all geotechnical design situations. This will represent a change from the present situation, where using the existing British Standards, there are separate codes for the design of foundations and retaining structures.

The introduction of Eurocode 7 will harmonise geotechnical designs in Ireland with those in other countries in Europe, but will not result in uniform designs throughout Europe as each national standards organisation will produce an annex stating

which Design Approach or Approaches and what partial factor values are to be used in the country it represents.

The introduction of Eurocode 7 will result in the harmonisation of geotechnical design with structural design with all designs being based on the same limit state design philosophy.

Eurocode 7 will also result in geotechnical design becoming more rational and less empirical. This will lead to a better understanding of geotechnics and hence better and safer geotechnical designs. This will be good for society as a whole. It should improve the image of geotechnical design and should enhance the image of the geotechnical profession.

References

- ENV 1991-1: 1994 *Eurocode 1 Basis of design and actions on structures: Part 1: Basis of design*, European Pre-standard, CEN, Brussels
- ENV 1997-1: 1994, *Eurocode 7 Geotechnical Design: Part 2:*

Figure 4: Variation in embedment depth with ϕ' for different design approaches

- Ground investigations and testing*, Adopted European Prestandard, CEN, Brussels
- prEN 1990: 2001 *Basis of Design*, Final Draft European Standard, CEN, Brussels
- prEN 1997-1::2002 *Eurocode 7 Geotechnical Design - Part 1: General Rules*, Draft European Standard, CEN, Brussels
- prEN 1997-2 *Eurocode 7 Geotechnical Design: Part 2: Ground investigation and testing*, First Draft of European Standard, CEN, Brussels
- Orr T.L.L. Orr (2002) *Eurocode 7 – A code for harmonised geotechnical design*, Proceedings International Workshop on Foundation Design Codes, Kamakura 2002, ed. Honjo et al., pp 3-15, Balkema
- Orr T.L.L & Farrell E.R. (1999) *Geotechnical Design to Eurocode 7*, Springer, London